

Involvement in Distractive Activities and Academic Performance of Students in Catarman National High School

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed at determining the level of students' involvement in distractive activities and the academic performance of Catarman National High School (CNHS) students in the Municipality of Catarman, Northern Samar. It looked into the level of involvement in distractive activities of CNHS students in terms of school gangs, vices and internet gaming; evaluate the level of academic performance of the students who are involved in distractive activities; and determine if there is a significant relationship between the students' level of involvement in distractive activities and their academic performance. The study consisted of 250 students from all year levels selected through stratified random sampling. This study employed descriptive-correlational research design. A questionnaire checklist was the main instrument in gathering the data. The data were treated statistically using frequency counts, weighted means, and percentages. To determine the significant relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variables the chi-square test was used. As to the salient findings of the study, the results showed that a majority of the students were not involved in the distractive activities. The findings revealed that the high school students' level of involvement in distractive activities such as school gangs and vices were found to be significantly but indirectly related to the academic performance of the students.

KEYWORDS: *distractive activities, academic performance, significant relationship*

1. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a time of extremely rapid change when young people begin to search for their identities, develop a meaningful interpersonal relationship, and establish a sense of independence, competence and self-esteem. In this period of life, young people are on the stage of inquisitiveness exploring, discovering, creating and experiencing all things that may attract their interests. They wish to try something, to do something, create something. As a result of these anything good or bad may happen.

Parents, elders and teachers are always on the watch of children who act in a way different from the actuations of normal children. Parents, elders and teachers do the role of guidance counselors. High school students who indulge in school gangs, vices and internet gaming ought to be guided. Their studies can be badly affected if too much of the activities outside the school are given more attention.

Many families with children in public schools have been alarmed with the kind of behavior their children have been exhibiting in and outside their homes. These children have changed dramatically in the way they dress, the language they use, their haircuts, and the kind of behavior they exhibit at home that causes conflicts among members of the family.

Remarkable and meaningful performance by the learners in school is the primary objective of education and working for

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these is the task of the school authorities as well as parents. The children need help with their academic skills, confidence and social, emotional skills to succeed in school. They must be able to understand the feelings of others, control their own feelings and behavior and get along with their peers and teachers. Early detection and intervention of social and emotional problems can have a long term effect on the developing child in major areas. The development of emotional, self-control and social ability in the early years plays a significant role in determining the way children think, learn, react to obstacle and develop relationships throughout their lives.

Academic performance is an important indicator of school success. It is not only associated with high school completion, but also the ability to successful transition into adult roles, to achieve economic self-efficacy and to become a productive member of the community.

But as they involved themselves and being influenced by school gang, internet gaming and vices, students' academic performance gradually changes and deteriorates. Some dropped out in the middle or even towards the end of the school year. There are some students who stopped going to school; yet, they continue recruiting more gang members. And as observed, most of the students who are gang members are no longer behaving well inside and outside the

classroom. The school authorities, parents and stakeholders, as care givers, are invaluable to the students in these turbulent years of their development, when they need help to rise from indecision to goal-directed, systematic action.

It is on the above concerns that this study is being conducted and brought into the open as to the level of involvement in distractive activities and academic performance of Catarman National High School students.

2. Objectives

This study aimed at determining the level of involvement in distractive activities and the level of academic performance of Catarman National High School students.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the students' level of involvement in distractive activities in terms of:
 - A. gangs;
 - B. vices;
 - C. internet gaming?
2. What is the level of the academic performance of the students in Catarman National High School?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of involvement in distractive activities and the academic performance of the students in terms of:
 - A. school gangs;
 - B. vices;
 - C. internet gaming?

3. Review of Literature

Because of the family's importance to the child and youth welfare the Family Code Title IX Chapter 1. Art. 209 specifically provides that the parents are obliged to support the child in terms of the child needs. Parents are morally and legally bound to take care of children and to impart them the ethical value, norms and standards. Pursuant to the natural right and duty of parents over the person and property of their un-emancipated children, parental authority and responsibility shall include the caring for and rearing them for civic consciousness and efficiency and the development of their moral, mental and physical character and well-being.

Barkadas are integral part of the school culture. As such, youth are exposed to the school gangs and violence of gang wars. Youth who lack of proper guidance often become members of these illegal organizations.

Gang issues are priority concerns for many urban and rural schools. Educators need to be aware and understand school gang prevention and preparedness before a crisis hits. The best interests of the children should be the first consideration in all actions concerning them, that should be undertaken by any public and private school and social institutions, courts law, administrative authorities. Every effort should be exerted to promote the welfare of the students and enhance their opportunities for a useful and happy life.

Arellano made a study to show the difficult misbehavior which are committed by high school students in the public and private co-educational secondary schools of Davao City. He concluded that students' misbehavior which were common and frequently committed by high school students were: (a) truancy (b) cheating (c) anger (d) absenteeism (e) vandalism (f) stealing.

Juanito Nielo Infante Jr. revealed in his findings that the concept of gangs or gangster for its gang member is that of "substitute family" where normal basic needs which they could not find with their regular families such as respect, the feeling of importance and recognition, and support are being fulfilled within the group. Although there was no definite set of goals among the gang members, loyalty appear to be a must among members. Everyone is expected to be loyal to the group or else suffers punishment for not doing so.

He cited that "conflict activities" among juvenile gangs was common among youthful groups. Norms which require involvement in physical combat against rival gang, hazing, defacement of properties, shop lifting, parties, and drugs are central to the behavioral standards of many juvenile groups. Initiation was a ritual used to determine the members extent of willingness to join gangs. During initiation, belts, paddles, branches of tree are usually used in hazing. At times sex was also used for initiating young girls to determine their willingness to join gangs.

Furthermore he explained that gang membership had contributed greatly to the negative behavior exhibited or manifested by the gang members. Family relationships were affected by the behavior exhibited by the gang member in their families. The absence of parental guidance had contributed also to such behavior. The school standing was affected by gang membership because most of the time these members would rather hang-out in their turf than to go to school. The teacher set very high standard for students that were difficult to achieve or reach thereby establishing a school that is oppressive and not caring or nurturing. The teacher also exhibited lack of understanding regarding the true nature of the problems at hand.

Dela Cruz cited that in De La Salle University (DLSU) many students were found addicted to on-line chat, one of the popular applications/services in the internet. The study reveals that the students' social life was severely affected, as they preferred engaging in on-line communication than interacting with their family and friends. The academic life also suffers as they mostly resorted to skipping classes just to be able to spend more time on the internet. On health trend, majority of DLSU students is addicted to chatting and had sleep disorder as they tried to stay awake and be on-line during wee hours.

Sagun in her study revealed the following results: Students identified type of computer games they played. Counter strike (2.19) got the highest rank followed by the family computer games (2.17), next is puzzles and board games (2.09), sports games (1.82) and lastly educational games (1.63).

4. Methodology

This study employed the descriptive design specifically correlational survey method. The descriptive method is a useful tool for fact finding. Since this study aimed to investigate students' level of involvement in distractive activities, this particular method was used. Correlational method was used to determine the extent to which different variables are related to each other in the population of interest.

The respondents of this study were the 250 or 10 percent of the CNHS students selected through stratified sampling representing the four year levels.

The study made use of two-part survey questionnaire. The first part dealt on the level of students' involvement in distractive activities in terms of school gang, vices and internet gaming; while determining the academic performance comprised the second part.

5. Results and Discussion

Table1 Distribution of Respondents' to Involvement in Distractive Activities

Distractive Activities	Frequency	Percentage
School Gangs	12	4.8
Vices	21	8.4
Internet Gaming	50	20
Not involved	167	66.8
Total	250	100

Table 1 shows the level of involvement in distractive activities of high school students in terms of school gangs, vices and internet gaming. Out of the 250 students, 167 or 66.8 percent were involved in distractive activities. Of these 83 high school students, 12 or 14.5% were involved in school gangs, 21 or 25.3% were indulged in vices, and 50 or 60.2% of the respondents were into internet gaming.

Those who were involved in internet gaming were observed to be interested because they wanted to play games in the guise of making their reports. These findings run counter with that of Infante's study that the school standing is affected by gang membership. In the study of Niemz et al., he stated that excessive use of the internet was causing academic problems. This suggests that internet gaming may have a detrimental effect on an individual's academic performance. The GPA versus internet gaming is more reliable because both involve a continuous measurement of engaged activity and performance. However, the present study negates such findings considering the majority were not involved in these distractive activities. Dela Cruz

revealed in her study that the students' academic life and social life were severely affected to be able to spend more time on the internet. However, Lagamon proved the insignificant relationship of computer games to students' school works and achievement.

A minority of students in CNHS were into vices. It is one manifestation that The Northern Samar Children's Welfare Code that prohibits the selling and giving liquor, cigarettes, rugby and other addictive substances to children is not yet fully implemented. Although there were 12 student-respondents who involved themselves in school gangs the number is quite insignificant as to the 160 respondents who did not involve themselves in it. The Catarman National High School has a number of student-based organizations, namely, Football Club, Chess Club, Dance Guild, Performing Arts, Boy Scouts of the Philippines, Girl Scouts of the Philippines, The Torch and SSG which can be one factor why only few of the respondents were involved in school gangs.

Table2 Distribution of Respondents' Level of Academic Performance

Grades	Frequency	Percentage
75-79	52	21
80-84	103	41
85-89	77	31
90-95	18	7
Total	250	100

Table 2 shows the data on students' grade point average in the third quarter. On the whole 52 or 21% of the respondents had average academic performance of 75% to 79%; 103 or 41% were in the 80% to 84% bracket; 77 or 31% were in the 85% to 89% bracket; and only 18 or 7% of the respondents were above average. Although majority of the respondents were in the average bracket, it shows that they are performing at a level much above than the failing mark. It can be inferred that students still prioritize their studies as evident in their grades.

Table3 Relationship between Distractive Activities and Academic Performance

Distractive Activities	Academic Performance				Total
	75-79	80-84	85-89	90-95	
School Gangs	7 (2.5)	5 (4.9)	0 (3.7)	0 (0.9)	12
Vices	17 (4.4)	4 (8.7)	0 (6.5)	0 (1.5)	21
Internet Gaming	0 (10.4)	30(20.6)	18(15.4)	2 (3.6)	50
Not Involved	28(34.7)	64(68.8)	59(51.4)	16(12.0)	167
Total	52	103	77	18	250

$\chi^2 C = 79.7$ $\chi^2 t = 16.9$ $df = 9$ $LS = .05$

Table 3 describes the relationship between distractive activities, namely: School gangs, vices and internet gaming and the academic performance of the student, namely: 75-79; 80-84; 85-89; and 90-95. It can be seen from Table 6 that the computed chi-square value of 79.9 is greater than the tabular chi-square value of 16.9 with 9 degrees of freedom at .05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between distractive activities and academic performance was rejected. It means that the distractive activities of the students influence their academic performance. This means that those who are involved in distractive activities have lower academic performance compared to those who are not involved.

6. Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the hereunder conclusions were derived.

While majority of the students are not involved in distractive activities, a significant number of CNHS high school students are involved in school gangs, vices, and internet gaming. It can be implied that these distractive activities could be a threat to students performance if not be treated seriously.

As regards academic performance, majority of the respondents were in the average bracket. It shows that they are performing at a level much above than the failing mark. It

can be implied that students still prioritize their studies as evident in their grades.

Students' involvement in school gangs and vices are significantly related to the academic performance of high school students. However, internet gaming is not significantly related to their academic performance. This indicates that the students' performance is affected by their membership in school gangs and indulging in vices, hence, they cannot perform well in their studies. The academic performance of the students is affected by school gangs and vices because most of the time these members would hang-out with their groups rather than going to school.

7. Recommendations

Grounded on the conclusions, the hereunder recommendations were drawn.

1. The administrators, teachers and parents are encouraged to orient students on the possible effects of school gangs, vices and excessive computer exposure habit on the academic performance and personal health and security of the students. They could provide guidelines to regulate their students.
2. Administrators should take a paradigm shift and take the lead in encouraging teachers to update their educational concept regarding the use of computer as a tool for innovative teaching and learning and divert students' attention on possible involvement in school gangs and vices to useful activities such as sports, and project exhibits.
3. Based on the outcome of the study that school gangs membership, vices and internet gaming has affected the academic performance of the students, a study on how the schools are responding to deviant problems of the students be conducted as well.
4. The Department of Education, as the Philippine lead implementing agency must encourage research studies to explore sound policies and strategies that will actually address problems related to school gangs, vices and internet gaming among students. With this, effectiveness of the school program is highly expected.
5. School managers, teachers, parents, GPTA officers and barangay officials should have closer coordination in

preventing the practice of school gangs, vices and internet gaming among students.

6. Student Government Officers, teachers, school officials, parents, GPTA/PTA officers, and barangay officials should regularly follow-up cases on school problems.

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